

An Attempted Synthesis of Oxyprotoberberine and a Synthesis of 3-Methoxyoxyprotoberberine.

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An unsuccessful attempt to synthesise oxyprotoberberine and tetrahydroprotoberberine, the parent substance of the berberine and palmatine group of alkaloids, for which the name "Berbin" has recently been suggested by Walter Awe (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1932, 270, 161), was first made by Haworth, Perkin and Pink (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1711). These compounds were first synthesised by one of us (S.N.C.) in 1927 (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2275). The melting point of tetrahydroprotoberberine was found to be 85°, and numerous derivatives of this compound were prepared. In the same year Kitasato prepared a compound having the melting point 254-60°, which he called tetrahydroprotoberberine (*Acta Phytochim.*, 1927, 3, 175). In view of this discrepancy, we sought to verify our results by synthesising tetrahydroprotoberberine by another method analogous to that employed by Perkin, Ray and Robinson for synthesising oxyberberine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 740). For this purpose the acid chloride of phthalide-carboxylic acid was condensed with β -phenylethylamine when the amide (I) (m.p. 155°) was formed. Unfortunately all attempts to convert the amide (I) into oxyprotoberberine (II) were unsuccessful, undoubtedly due to the absence of

activating methoxy groups. When phosphorus pentachloride was used to effect cyclisation in place of phosphorus oxychloride, a

crystalline substance (m.p. 153°) was obtained in a poor yield. This substance was found to be quite different from oxyprotoberberine synthesised previously and its analysis did not agree with the values calculated for oxyprotoberberine.

While these experiments were in progress, Wolfgang Leithe published a paper which fully confirmed the results obtained previously by one of us (S.N.C.). He synthesised tetrahydroprotoberberine anew by a slight modification of our previous method and found its melting point to be 85° (*Ber.*, 1930, **63**, 2343). In view of this work, and the fact that Kitasato withdrew his statement in a private communication to one of us, further work on this subject was discontinued.

Incidentally, 3-methoxyoxyprotoberberine (IV) was synthesised, a synthesis which is of interest from the point of view of the determination of ease of formation of alkaloids of berberine-palmatine type containing no pyrocatechol nuclei (*cf.* Chakravarti, Haworth and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2267, 2275; Chakravarti and Perkin, *ibid.*, 1929, 196).

The acid chloride of phthalide-carboxylic acid condensed readily in benzene solution with β -*m*-methoxyphenylethylamine yielding phthalide-carboxy- β -*m*-methoxyphenylethylamide (III), m.p. 105°. When this was heated with phosphorus oxychloride and the product decomposed with ice, a basic substance separated (on basification of the aqueous solution), which, on reduction with zinc dust and acetic acid, was converted into a pale yellow substance, m.p. 143°, having all the properties of a compound of the oxyberberine type, and this is doubtless the 3-methoxyoxyprotoberberine (IV).

The point of general interest which emerges from this synthesis is that the synthetical experiments described proceed as readily when

only one methoxy group is present in the *meta* position to ethylamine group, as they do in the case of the corresponding syntheses in the berberine group. The ease of formation in this case is doubtless due to the presence of an activating *para*-methoxy group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phthalide-carboxy-β-phenylamide, (I).—Phthalide carboxylic acid (10 g.) prepared by the reduction of phthalonic acid which in its turn was prepared by the oxidation of naphthalene (Compare Ullmann and Uzbachian, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1805; Graebe and Trumpy, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 373), was thoroughly mixed with the equivalent amount of phosphorus pentachloride and heated on the steam-bath for 3 hours. Phosphorus oxychloride formed was then completely removed by distillation *in vacuo*, and the residue dissolved in dry benzene and added gradually to a dry benzene solution of β-phenylethylamine (prepared from 9 g. of the hydrochloride). After remaining overnight, the mixture was heated on the steam-bath for ½ hour, cooled, and washed successively with sodium carbonate solution and dilute hydrochloric acid, and dried over sodium sulphate. On distilling off most of the benzene, the amide separated as a white powder (yield almost quantitative). On repeated recrystallisations from ethyl alcohol it melts at 155°. (Found: C, 72·8; H, 5·3. C₁₇H₁₅O₃N requires C, 72·6; H, 5·3 per cent.)

An attempted synthesis of oxyprotoberberine, (II).—An attempt was made to convert *phthalide-carboxy-β-phenylethylamide* (I) into oxyprotoberberine, by treating the amide with phosphorus oxychloride and then treating the basic substance thus formed with zinc dust and glacial acetic acid exactly under conditions described by Perkin, Ray and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) for converting the piperonylethylamide of meconine carboxylic acid into oxyberberine (*cf.* Chakravarti and Perkin, *loc. cit.*). The final product obtained was a brown resinous substance which could not be obtained in a crystalline form, and which could not be further examined owing to the very poor yield. Phosphorus pentoxide in boiling xylene solution was then tried as the cyclising agent. Again a very poor yield of the same resinous substance was obtained. When, however, phosphorus pentachloride was used as the cyclising agent, a distinctly crystalline pale yellow substance was obtained, which was repeatedly crystallised from methyl

alcohol in beautiful needles, m. p. 153°, and is very readily soluble in the usual organic solvents. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 4.45; N, 4.3. $C_{17}H_{13}ON$ requires C, 82.6; H, 5.3; N, 5.7 per cent.). We are indebted for this microanalysis to Dr. Ing. A. Schoeller of Berlin.

The substance thus formed differs markedly in its properties from oxyprotoberberine synthesised by one of us (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2280), and it could not be further investigated owing to the small amount of the substance at our disposal.

Phthalide-carboxy-β-m-methoxyphenylethylamide, (III).—*β-m*-Methoxyphenylethylamide was prepared by a slight modification of the method previously described by one of us (Chakravarti, Haworth and Perkin, *loc. cit.*), *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde being methylated in the following manner in more than 90 per cent. yield. 50 G. of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde dissolved in 200 c. c. of 10 p.c. sodium hydroxide solution. was treated gradually with constant shaking with 55 c.c. of dimethyl sulphate. When all the dimethyl sulphate had been added, the mixture was further shaken for a few minutes and then warmed on the water-bath for 1 hour. *m*-Methoxybenzaldehyde formed was then separated in the usual manner. *m*-Methoxyphenylethylamine was then condensed with the acid chloride of phthalide-carboxylic acid exactly under the conditions described above for the amide (I). *Phthalide-carboxy-β-m-methoxyphenylethylamide* was thus obtained in almost quantitative yield. It crystallises in colourless plates, m. p. 105°. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 5.6. $C_{18}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 69.4; H, 5.5 per cent.).

3-Methoxyoxyprotoberberine, (IV).—The amide (III) (12 g.) was mixed with freshly distilled phosphorus oxychloride (120 c.c.), and the mixture heated for 6 hours on the water-bath. A copious evolution of hydrogen chloride was observed, the liquid gradually undergoing a change in colour through yellow to dark red. The mixture was decomposed by means of cold water and the liquid filtered, leaving a dark resinous residue. The yellow filtrate was then basified when an orange-red precipitate was obtained. This substance was collected, well washed with water, dried in the air, and boiled with zinc dust (25 g.) and glacial acetic acid (135 c.c.) for 5 minutes. Then more of zinc dust (25 g.) added and the whole mixture further boiled for ½ hour. The cooled solution was diluted with a large amount of ethyl acetate, filtered and washed several times with dilute hydrochloric acid, then with aqueous sodium hydroxide and finally with water. The solution was dried over potassium carbonate and

the solvent removed by distillation. A yellow crystalline residue was left behind, which was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol, as beautiful needles, m. p. 143°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 78.3; H, 5.5. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 78.0; H, 5.4 per cent.).

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